

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDIES ON FERROUS COMPLEXES OF
QUINOLINE- AND PYRIDINE-CARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART II.
FERROUS PICOLINATE SYSTEM

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The strongly coloured, highly soluble ferrous complex with picolinic acid forms the subject matter of the present investigation in respect of its usefulness for the estimation of iron. The coloured complex has been found to develop its maximum colour intensity between p_H 5.2 and 9. The presence of KCN, so also of pyridine to some extent, increases this colour intensity with an absorption maximum lying at about 440 $m\mu$. The coloured system, with or without KCN, obeys Beer's law.

The composition of the coloured complex is given by 1 Fe^{II} : 3 acid, with an instability constant 5.07×10^{-12} . The complex thus acquires the character of a univalent anion.

In continuation of our previous communication (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 297) we are now in a position to report the results of our investigation on the highly coloured ferrous picolinate system. Picolinic acid was first employed by Majumdar and Sen (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 8, 369) for the colorimetric estimation of ferrous iron, and they also determined the composition of the coloured complex by Job's method (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928), which was given by 1 Fe^{II} : 2 acid. This seems to suggest that the complex must be a non-electrolyte; this cannot, however, be reconciled with its extreme solubility. The instability constant of the complex was found by Majumdar and Sen to be 4.23×10^{-8} . On the other hand, Shimra *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1954, 75, 44) showed that composition of the coloured ferrous picolinate complex should be represented by 1 Fe^{II} : 3 acid. This discrepancy in the results of the two sets of workers necessitated a re-investigation of the problem.

In the present work, the composition of the coloured complex in solution has been found to correspond to that given by the Japanese workers, namely 1 Fe^{II} : 3 acid, as shown below :

This can occur only as an anion in solution, which is supported by the fact that the colour intensity increases with the p_H of the solution and becomes constant in the alkaline region. Determination of the instability constant of the complex also leads to a value differing widely from that of Majumdar and Sen (*loc. cit.*) and is given by 5.07×10^{-12} .

The colour of ferrous picolinate, like that of ferrous quinaldinate, is also highly intensified by the addition of potassium cyanide and to some extent by pyridine.

The colour intensity in the presence of cyanide was employed by the previous workers (*loc. cit.*) for the colorimetric estimation of ferrous iron. In solutions containing cyanide, a molecule of picolinic acid is probably replaced by a corresponding number of cyanogen groups. As in the case of quinaldinic acid, the colour intensity of the ferrous picolinate system increases with the increasing amount of potassium cyanide and then reaches a maximum and constant value, beyond which no further change occurs. The $\lambda_{\max}$ remains, however, unchanged, which is rather unusual. In the presence of a moderate or smaller amount of potassium cyanide, the colour of the ferrous picolinate system behaves similarly to that of ferrous quinaldinate with time. After 3 or 4 days a pink tint appears in the solution and the absorption maximum shifts towards the ultraviolet. In the presence of a large excess of KCN, the colour remains practically unchanged for several days.

Addition of pyridine also intensifies the colour of the ferrous picolinate complex in solution to a certain extent, but unlike potassium cyanide it does not lead to a maximum or constant value. The intensity of the colour continues to increase with the increasing amount of pyridine added, and finally the absorption maximum shifts rapidly towards the ultraviolet, when a certain concentration of pyridine in the system is exceeded.

EXPERIMENTAL

Picolinic acid was prepared by the oxidation of α -picoline (Ramage and Clemo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 440). A Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer and guaranteed quality chemicals were employed for experimental work. The colour of the ferrous picolinate complex is yellow and the absorption maximum lies in the region of 440 m μ . The maximum colour formation occurs above p_H 5.2 and the colour intensity remains practically unchanged up to p_H 9. The system was found to obey Beer's law for concentrations above 5 p.p.m of ferrous ion, and gives a sensitivity of 0.056 γ/cm^2 (Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, New York, p. 47). Potassium cyanide intensifies the colour of the complex, though to a lesser extent than in the case of ferrous quinaldinate system, without any change in the wave-length for absorption maximum. The cyanide-containing system also obeys Beer's law and its sensitivity rises to 0.028 γ of ferrous ion/cm² (Sandell, *loc. cit.*). Three to four times the theoretical quantity of picolinic acid is required for the maximum colour development of ferrous picolinate. A quantity of potassium cyanide, at least 80 to 100 times that of ferrous ion present, is required for the maximum intensification of colour. The colour system with or without the cyanide or pyridine is quite stable at room temperature and remains almost unchanged for about 24 hours.

Wave-length of Absorption maximum ($\lambda_{\max}$).—The same procedure as in the case of ferrous quinaldinate system (*loc. cit.*) was followed. The reagent blank and the iron solution (ferric nitrate + $NH_4OH.HCl$) separately showed negligible or no absorption at or about 440 m μ . Fig. 1 shows the optical density values

of the coloured complex at different wave-lengths with or without KCN. The colour formation is instantaneous as in the case of quinaldinic acid (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 1

Ferric nitrate (50 p.p.m of Fe), 10 c.c. $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (5%), 5 c.c. Picolinic acid (1%), 10 c.c. KCN (1%), 10 c.c. Total volume, 50 c.c. Cell used, 1 cm.

Beer's Law.—The coloured complex of ferrous picolinate with or without cyanide obeys Beer's law. This is evident from the optical density values given in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

Ferric nitrate (50 p.p.m Fe), 10 c.c. $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (5%), 5 c.c. Resagent (1%), 10 c.c. KCN (1%), 10 c.c. Total volume, 50 c.c. Cell, 1 cm. 440 mμ.

Influence of Cyanide and Pyridine Concentrations.—The effect of the concentration of cyanide and of pyridine on the coloured system is shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. With the addition of pyridine the colour intensity at 440 m μ rises slowly and continuously, but with very large excess the absorption maximum shifts abruptly towards the ultraviolet region. It might be noted here that from concentrated solutions of ferrous picolinate and pyridine no compound could be isolated unlike the case of ferrous quinaldinate.

FIG. 3.

Fe-amm. sulphate (70 p.p.m. Fe) containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (1%), 10 c.c. Reagent (1%), 10 c.c. KCN (700 p.p.m.), x c.c. Total volume, 50 c.c. Cell, 1 cm. $m\mu$ 440. p_H before addition of KCN, 6 (approx.).

FIG. 4.

Ferric nitrate (50 p.p.m. Fe), 10 c.c. $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (5%), 5 c.c. Picolinic acid (1%), 10 c.c. Pyridine, x c.c. Total volume, 50 c.c. Cell, 1 cm. $m\mu$ 440.

It should be pointed out here that with the increasing amount of pyridine and of potassium cyanide, the p_H may rise up to 7 and 9 respectively. As with the quinaldinic acid, the increase of colour intensity produced by potassium cyanide or pyridine is not due to this increase in the p_H value of the medium. This is clear from the following values of optical density for one and the same concentration of iron at the same p_H of solutions with KCN or pyridine and without any such addition.

[p_H 6.9, $m\mu$ 440, cell 1 cm, reagent in excess].

I. (with no KCN or pyridine)	0.178
II. (with KCN)	0.348
III. (with pyridine)	0.191

Composition of the Coloured Complex of Ferrous Iron with Picolinic Acid.—The composition of the coloured complex was determined spectrophotometrically by Job's method at p_H 5.99 with the use of sodium acetate—acetic acid buffer and in presence of sufficient KNO_3 , as in the case of ferrous quinaldinate system. The results of measurement are shown in Fig. 5 (A, B). From the curves it is clear that the composition of the complex is represented by 1 Fe^{II} : 3 acid.

FIG. 5A

Fe-ammon. sulphate (0.0025M) containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (1%), x c.c. Picolinic acid (0.0025M), y c.c. KNO_3 (1M) soln., 10 c.c. Buffer (5.99 p_H), 18 c.c. Total volume, 50 c.c. Cell used, 2 cm.

FIG. 5B

Fe-ammon. sulphate (0.005M) containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (1%), x c.c. Picolinic acid (0.005M), y c.c. All other conditions are exactly the same as in Fig. 5A.

Instability Constant of the Coloured Complex.—The instability constant of the coloured complex of ferrous picolinate can be calculated from the following equation (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*)

$$K_c = \frac{[\text{Fe}^{2+}]}{[(\text{FeP}_3)^-]} \times \frac{K_a^3 \{ [P_t] - 3[(\text{FeP}_3)^-] \}^3}{K_a^3 + [\text{H}^+]^3} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

All the symbols have the same significance as indicated in Part I (*loc. cit.*). P represents a molecule of picolinic acid or a picolinate ion and P_t , total picolinic acid. $K_a = 3.0 \times 10^{-6}$ from the literature (Hodgman, "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", Chemical Rubber Publishing Co., Cleveland, Ohio, 1955-56, p. 1645), $[\text{H}^+]$ is obtained directly from p_H measurements, $[(\text{FeP}_3)^-]$ from optical density, and all the other factors are known from the experimental conditions. Tables IA and IB record the values of measurement for the coloured complex in equilibrium.

TABLE IA

Ferrous ammonium sulphate (0.002M) containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (1%), x c.c. Picolinic acid (0.005 M), y c.c. KNO_3 (1 M) soln., 10 c.c., Buffer (p_H 5.99), 18 c.c. Cell, 2 cm. 440 m μ .

Picolinic acid (c.c.)	...	8	9	10(a)	11(b)	12(c)	13(d)	14
Fe-soln. (c.c.)	...	12	11	10	9	8	7	6
O.D.	...	0.406	0.467	0.502	0.519	0.528	0.498	0.458

TABLE IB

Ferrous ammonium sulphate (0.01 M) containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (1%), x c.c. Picolinic acid (0.005M), y c.c. All the other conditions are exacty the same as in Table IA.

Picolinic acid (c.c.)	...	5(e)	6.0	6.65	7.5	8(f)	8.5	9(g)
Fe-soln. (c.c.)	...	5	4	1.35	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.0
O.D.	...	0.243	0.292	0.346	0.395	0.479	0.429	0.339

Now from the equation (1), K_c was calculated for a, b, c, d, e, f and g. The results are collected in Table II.

TABLE II

$$K_a = 3 \times 10^{-6} \quad [H^+] = 0.1023 \times 10^{-6}$$

	a	b	c	d	e	f	g
Pt	1.00×10^{-3}	1.10×10^{-3}	1.20×10^{-3}	1.30×10^{-3}	5.00×10^{-4}	8.00×10^{-4}	9.00×10^{-4}
FeP ₃	2.53×10^{-4}	2.61×10^{-4}	2.66×10^{-4}	2.50×10^{-4}	1.22×10^{-4}	2.11×10^{-4}	1.70×10^{-4}
Fe	1.47×10^{-4}	9.90×10^{-5}	5.40×10^{-5}	3.00×10^{-5}	8.78×10^{-4}	1.89×10^{-4}	3.00×10^{-5}
K_c	3.37×10^{-12}	5.01×10^{-12}	5.47×10^{-12}	8.28×10^{-12}	7.19×10^{-12}	1.73×10^{-12}	4.34×10^{-12}

Hence, the mean $K_c = 5.07 \times 10^{-12}$.

Majumdar and Sen (*loc. cit.*) gave, however, a value of 4.53×10^{-5} for K_c , assuming that the composition is given by 1Fe^{II} : 2 acid on the basis of their experimental results, which we failed to confirm.

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